

Original Article

In vitro Evaluation of Antiinflammatory, Antioxidant Activity of Pomegranate Peel Extract Mediated Calcium Sulphate, Titanium Dioxide Nano Composite

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Pomegranate peel is considered to be a reservoir of biologically active compounds, the presence of which provides anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties to the peel extract. Calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide osteoconductive materials used for bone regeneration. In the present study, a green synthesized pomegranate peel extract mediated (PPE) calcium sulphate, (CaSO₄) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nano composite (PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC) was formulated, and its biological properties, specifically antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects were evaluated. The objectives were to green synthesize pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nano composite and subsequently evaluate its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. Anti-inflammatory activity was evaluated using, Bovine serum albumin denaturation assay (BSA), Egg albumin denaturation assay (EA) and was compared with Diclofenac sodim as standard. Antioxidant activity was measured using 2,2 Diphenyl-1-Picryl hydraxylhydrate (DPPH) assay, H₂O₂ assay, Ferric Reducing Antioxidant power (FRAP) assay. Comparison made with Ascorbic acid as standard. Anti-inflammatory activity was seen with all concentrations of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC and in all concentrations there is significant difference between the test material and the standard P<0.05. Significant difference was found for the antioxidant activity between PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC and standard in all concentrations (P<0.05). The study concluded that PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC has Anti-inflammatory and Antioxidant activity and it is concentration dependent.

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Introduction

Calcium sulphate (CaSO₄) is a mineral that exist in nature, its use in medicine dates back to 12th century. Due to its ability to conduct bone calcium sulphate was used to fill large bony defects [1]. During bone augmentation calcium sulphate acts as a reservoir of calcium ions, forms a scaffold for bone formation, undergoes complete resorption and the rate of resorption is equivalent to the new bone formation with minimal inflammatory response, these quality makes calcium sulphate an ideal material for bone regeneration [2,3]. Regeneration of bone with calcium sulphate is reported to be due its similarity to the mineral composition of bone. In

addition to above mentioned properties calcium sulphate provides structural support, inhibits fibrous tissue ingrowth, facilitates early infiltration of osteoprogenitor cells, and acts as a barrier, restricting connective tissue growth from nearby periosteum. Additionally, calcium sulphate appears to promote the development of blood vessels, osteogenic cells, and leaves behind calcium phosphate residues which closely resemble bone particles, causing no immune response and being well accepted, therefore Calcium sulphate is considered as a safe material for augmenting the defects in the bone [4,5]. Literature gives evidence that the Nanocrystalline form of calcium sulphate can act as a ceramic matrix, scaffold, and vehicle for delivering growth factors for osseous regeneration. It supports osteoblastic cell activity, is biocompatible, and may deliver platelet-derived growth factor and bone morphogenetic protein-2 (BMP-2) [6].

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Investigators have reported that titanium dioxide (TiO_2) in both its pure and pigmented forms, are biocompatible and exhibits excellent osteoconductive properties. It has shown to be effective in augmenting bony defects, making it a promising material for such applications [7]. TiO_2 is not only cost-effective but also largely non-toxic. Nanostructured TiO_2 has a wide range of applications due to its nanoscale characteristics, low toxicity, good biocompatibility, unique properties, and diverse fabrication methods. Among these nanostructures, titania nanotubes (NTs) are widely used for coating implant surfaces. The porous structure of TiO_2 NTs promotes bone regeneration and repair, making them ideal for enhancing bone tissue growth and the biological fixation of implants [8].

TiO_2 nanoparticles (NPs) are chemically stable, exhibit antibacterial properties, and are less toxic compared to other nanostructures. When exposed to a biological environment, blood plasma proteins and ions selectively adsorb onto the outer surface. Additionally, titanium dioxide nanoparticles have been shown to aid in the osseointegration process of titanium dental implants, helping to reduce the risk of prosthetic failures. When the effects of titanium dioxide nanoparticles on osteoblast mineralization were evaluated, it was found that titanium dioxide nanoparticles did not affect osteoblast viability in cell models, nor did they alter the osteoblast morphology or the spherical shape of the 3D model. However, they were shown to stimulate an increase in calcium deposition, indicating the activation of the mineralization process. Alkaline phosphatase synthesis and calcium labelling further demonstrated that TiO_2 NPs enhanced osteoblast differentiation, leading to increased mineralization [9].

Investigators report that Nanostructured materials increases surface area, and modify the surface topography to resemble natural bone. This can improve the interaction between bone cells and implants. studies have also demonstrated that the use of titanium dioxide nanotubes can enhance osteoblast adhesion by up to 400%, and leads to higher levels of alkaline phosphate and mineralization compared to non-modified TiO_2 [10]. Titanium dioxide nanoparticles synthesized using *Mucuna pruriens* seed extract is reported to have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties [11]. *Paniculata* synthesized TiO_2 nanoparticles showed the increased concentration of the antioxidant activity [12]. Studies in literature have reported that a calcium sulfate and titanium dioxide composite can serve as an osseoconductive scaffold, promoting the formation of new regenerative bone [13].

Pomegranate peel is rich in phenolic compounds, including tannins (such as punicalagin, punicalin, ellagic acid, and gallic acid) and flavonoids (such as catechin, anthocyanins, and other complex flavonoids). These compounds give the peel an exceptionally high antioxidant capacity, reported to be around 10 times greater than that of the fruit's edible parts. This unique biochemical profile is responsible for many of the pharmacological effects attributed to pomegranate [14]. Studies have shown that biologically active compounds in pomegranate peel extract can directly influence bone cell differentiation, leading to an improved balance between bone resorption and formation, along with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects in the bone microenvironment. The anti-inflammatory components of pomegranate peel extract—punicalagin, punicalin, stricinin A, and granatin B—significantly reduce the production of nitric oxide and prostaglandins by inhibiting the expression of proinflammatory proteins [15].

Pomegranate peel extract when used as a dietary supplement is reported to increase bone mass and improve the microarchitecture of bone tissue in individuals with osteoporosis [16]. Pomegranate

peel extract enriched diet improves bone mineralization by increasing osteogenic transcription factors and stimulating activity of bone maker protein, i.e. alkaline phosphatase (ALP) it also reduced osteoclast differentiation and bone resorption [17]. Oral supplementation of pomegranate peel extract can increase vitamin D absorption; thus it may promote the bone healing process [18]. Local application of *Punicagranatum* Seed Oil along with gelatine sponge enhanced bone regeneration and accelerated bone healing [19]. Researchers have also observed a notable elevation in ALP activity with pomegranate extracts, providing further evidence for its proposed involvement in regulating the differentiation of osteoblastic cells [20]. Extracts obtained from pomegranate are powerful vehicles of antioxidants and anti-inflammatory compounds, which can effectively aid in the restoration of bone health [21].

Extensive literature supports the use of CaSO_4 and TiO_2 as osteoconductive materials. The osteogenic impact of various pomegranate extracts has been substantiated by the presence of biologically active compounds, particularly abundant in the pomegranate peel. Identifying and assessing compounds with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties presents new therapeutic possibilities in the field of bone regeneration. Hence, it is crucial to explore their potential therapeutic applications, particularly in the context of bone regeneration. In this study, a green synthesized Pomegranate peel extract mediated (PPE) mediated calcium sulphate, (CaSO_4) and Titanium dioxide (TiO_2) nano composite (PPE CaSO_4 TiO_2 NC) was formulated, and its biological properties, specifically antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects were examined. The objectives included the preparation of PPE, the green synthesis of PPE mediated CaSO_4 and TiO_2 nano composite and the evaluation of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of PPE CaSO_4 TiO_2 NC.

Materials and Methods

The present in vitro study was designed and carried out at the Nanobiomedicine Laboratory, Department of Pharmacology, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Chennai The Ethical Committee of the Institution approved the project (BRULAC/SDCH/SIMATS/IAEC/05-2022/125). The study evaluated the anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant, activity of the freshly prepared Pomegranate peel extract mediated Calcium sulphate and Titanium dioxide Nano composite Bone graft material.

Preparation of pomegranate peel extract

Pomegranate fruits were sourced from a local market, and the peels were separated, chopped into small pieces, and air-dried at room temperature. One gram of the dried pomegranate peel was mixed with 100 mL of distilled water and heated to 70°C for 20 minutes using a heating mantle. The mixture was then filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper to obtain the extract. The resulting solution was stored at 4°C in a refrigerator, to be later used for preparing bone graft material. This method is commonly used to extract bioactive compounds from pomegranate peel for potential biomedical applications.

Preparation of pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide nano composite bone graft material (PPE CaSO_4 TiO_2 NC)

Initially, 0.35g of titanium oxide was dissolved in 25mL of distilled water, followed by the addition of 25mL of filtered pomegranate peel extract. Simultaneously, 0.5g of calcium sulphate was dissolved in 25mL of distilled water with 25mL of filtered pomegranate peel extract added. Both mixtures were stirred on a magnetic stirrer at 600 rpm for 24 hours. After this, the pomegranate peel extract

mediated titanium dioxide nanoparticles (TiO₂ NPs) and pomegranate peel mediated calcium sulphate (CaSO₄) solutions were combined to form a 100mL solution. This mixture underwent further stirring on a magnetic stirrer for 48 hours at 600 rpm. Subsequently, the solution was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes, resulting in separation of the supernatant and formation of a pellet. The pellet was then dried in a hot air oven at 70°C to obtain a powdered format.

Characterization

The synthesized bone graft material ie PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC was characterized by various techniques using scanning electron microscopy, elemental dispersive analysis, fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction analysis.

Anti-inflammatory activity

The anti-inflammatory activity of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC was tested using two assays namely egg albumin denaturation assay and bovine serum albumin denaturation assay.

Egg albumin denaturation assay

Egg albumin denaturation assay (EA) was done as follows, 5ml solution was made using 2.8ml of freshly manufactured, pH-6.3 phosphate buffered saline and 0.2ml of chicken egg albumin extraction. The PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC of different concentrations Viz.10µL, 20µL, 30µL, 40µL, 50µL were prepared. Diclofenac sodium was the positive control. The mixes were then heated in a water bath for 15 minutes at 37°C. The samples were then allowed to cool to ambient temperature, and absorbance at 660 nm was measured.

Bovine serum albumin denaturation assay

The anti-inflammatory activity of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC was tested by the following convention proposed by Muzushima and Kabayashi with modifications. 0.05 mL of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC of various concentrations (10µL, 20µL, 30µL, 40µL, 50µL) were added to 0.45 mL bovine serum albumin (1% aqueous solution) and the pH of the mixture was acclimated to 6.3 using 1N hydrochloric acid. These samples were incubated at room temperature for 20 min and then heated at 55 °C for 30 min in a water bath. The temperature of the samples was lowered and the absorbance was estimated by spectrophotometry at 660 nm. Diclofenac Sodium was used as the standard. Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) is utilized as a control.

Percentage of protein denaturation was determined by the following equation,

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = (\text{abs.}_{\text{control}} - \text{abs.}_{\text{sample}}) / \text{abs.}_{\text{control}} \times 100$$

Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC was tested using three methods, of which two – DPPH and H₂O₂ - were based on the free-radical scavenging capacity of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC. The third one, FRAP was based on measuring the iron-reducing capacity.

DPPH assay

The assay used a commercially available free radical 2,2 diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl hydrate (DPPH) which is soluble in methanol, and the antioxidant activity was measured by the decrease in absorbance at 515 nm. PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC of various concentrations 10µL,

Table 1: Comparison between anti-inflammatory activities obtained in different concentrations in EA, BSA assay

Test	Concentration	% of inhibition	N	Mean	S.D.	S.E. Mean	p-value
EA	10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	52.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	55.00	0.943	0.298	
	20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	61.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	64.00	0.943	0.298	
	30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	68.00	0.943	0.298	0.029
		Standard	10	69.00	0.943	0.298	
	40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	68.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	72.00	0.943	0.298	
	50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	76.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	81.00	0.943	0.298	
BSA	10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	43.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	47.00	0.943	0.298	
	20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	57.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	60.00	0.943	0.298	
	30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	69.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	72.00	0.943	0.298	
	40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	75.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	78.00	0.943	0.298	
	50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	80.00	0.943	0.298	<0.001*
		Standard	10	84.00	0.943	0.298	

** p value <0.05 shows statistical significance – SD standard deviation, SE standard error

Table 2: t-test for Equality of Means (EA, BSA assay)

Test	Concentration	% of inhibition	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
EA	10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-7.115	18	<0.001*	-3.000	0.422	-3.886	-2.114
		Standard	-7.115	18.000					
	20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-7.115	18	<0.001*	-3.000	0.422	-3.886	-2.114
		Standard	-7.115	18.000					
	30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-2.372	18	.029	-1.000	0.422	-1.886	-.114
		Standard	-2.372	18.000					
	40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-9.487	18	<0.001*	-4.000	0.422	-4.886	-3.114
		Standard	-9.487	18.000					
	50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-11.859	18	<0.001*	-5.000	0.422	-5.886	-4.114
		Standard	-11.859	18.000					
BSA	10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-9.487	18	<0.001*	-4.000	0.422	-4.886	-3.114
		Standard	-9.487	18.000					
	20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-7.115	18	<0.001*	-3.000	0.422	-3.886	-2.114
		Standard	-7.115	18.000					
	30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-7.115	18	<0.001*	-3.000	0.422	-3.886	-2.114
		Standard	-7.115	18.000					
	40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-7.115	18	<0.001*	-3.000	0.422	-3.886	-2.114
		Standard	-7.115	18.000					
	50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-9.487	18	<0.001*	-4.000	0.422	-4.886	-3.114
		Standard	-9.487	18.000					

** p value <0.05 shows statistical significance

20µL, 30µL, 40µL, 50µL was prepared and mixed with 1 ml of 0.1 mM DPPH in methanol and 450 µL of 50 mM Tris HCl buffer (pH 7.4) and was incubated for 30 minutes. Later, the reduction in the quantity of DPPH free radicals was assessed depending on the absorbance at 515 nm. Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) was employed as control. The percentage of inhibition was determined by the following equation,

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = (\text{abs.}_{\text{control}} - \text{abs.}_{\text{sample}}) / \text{abs.}_{\text{control}} \times 100$$

Hydroxyl radical scavenging assay

The assay was performed as described by Halliwell with minor modifications. All the solutions were prepared freshly. 1.0mL of the reaction mixture contained the following: 100µL of 28mM of 2-deoxy-2-ribose (dissolved in phosphate buffer 7.4), 500µL solution of various concentrations of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC (10µL,

20µL, 30µL, 40µL, 50µL), 200µL of 200µM FeCl₃ and 1.04mM EDTA (1:1 v/v), 100µL H₂O₂ (1.0mM) and 100µL ascorbic acid (1.0mM). After incubating the reactant mixture for a period of 1 hour at 37°C the extent of deoxyribose degradation was measured by the Thiobarbituric Acid (TBA) reaction. The absorbance was measured at about 532nm against the blank solution. Vitamin E was used as the positive control.

FRAP Assay

Acetate buffer 300 mM, pH 3.6: 3.1g sodium acetate trihydrate was taken and 16 ml of glacial acetic acid was added to it and the volume was made up to 1 L with distilled water (a), TPTZ (2, 4, 6-tripyridyl-s- triazine): (M.W. 312.34) 10 mM in 40 mM HCl (M.W. 36.46) (b), and (c) FeCl₃. 6 H₂O: (M.W. 270.30), 20 mM. The working FRAP reagent was prepared by mixing a, b and c in the ratio of 10:1:1 just before the testing. Standard was ferrous sulphate heptahydrate

Table 3: Comparison between different concentrations of EA and BSA assay (ANOVA)

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
EA	Between Groups	3240.000	4	810.000	911.250	<0.001*
	Within Groups	40.000	45	.889		
	Total	3280.000	49			
BSA	Between Groups	8888.000	4	2222.000	2499.750	<0.001*
	Within Groups	40.000	45	.889		
	Total	8928.000	49			

** p value <0.05 shows statistical significance

Table 4: Multiple comparisons made by Tukey HSD on values obtained in EA, BSA assay

Test	Concentration	Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
EA	10 µL	20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-10.1981	-7.8019
		30 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-17.1981	-14.8019
		40 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-17.1981	-14.8019
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-25.1981	-22.8019
	20 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	7.8019	10.1981
		30 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-8.1981	-5.8019
		40 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-8.1981	-5.8019
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-16.1981	-13.8019
	30 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	14.8019	17.1981
		20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	5.8019	8.1981
		40 µL	0.42164	1.000	-1.1981	1.1981
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-9.1981	-6.8019
	40 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	14.8019	17.1981
		20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	5.8019	8.1981
		30 µL	0.42164	1.000	-1.1981	1.1981
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-9.1981	-6.8019
	50 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	22.8019	25.1981
		20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	13.8019	16.1981
		30 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	6.8019	9.1981
		40 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	6.8019	9.1981
BSA	10 µL	20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-15.1981	-12.8019
		30 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-27.1981	-24.8019
		40 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-33.1981	-30.8019
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-38.1981	-35.8019
	20 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	12.8019	15.1981
		30 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-13.1981	-10.8019
		40 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-19.1981	-16.8019
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-24.1981	-21.8019
	30 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	24.8019	27.1981
		20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	10.8019	13.1981
		40 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-7.1981	-4.8019
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-12.1981	-9.8019
	40 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	30.8019	33.1981
		20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	16.8019	19.1981
		30 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	4.8019	7.1981
		50 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-6.1981	-3.8019
	50 µL	10 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	35.8019	38.1981
		20 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-15.1981	-12.8019
		30 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-27.1981	-24.8019
		40 µL	0.42164	<0.001*	-33.1981	-30.8019

** p value <0.05 shows statistical significance

(FeSO₄ · 7 H₂O): 0.1 - 1.5 mM in methanol. All the reagents were procured from Merck (Germany) company [38]. 3.6 mL of FRAP solution was added to 0.4 mL of distilled water and was incubated at 37°C for 5 min. Then this solution was mixed with various concentrations of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC (10µL, 20µL, 30µL, 40µL, 50µL) and was incubated at 37°C for 10 min. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 593 nm. Calibration curve was constructed on the basis of five concentrations of FeSO₄ · 7H₂O (0.1, 0.4, 0.8, 1, 1.12, 1.5 mM) and the absorbance values were measured as for sample solutions.

Statistical Analysis

The results were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis using

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The independent t-test, ANOVA, and Tukey's HSD were used for statistical analysis. A p-value less than 0.05 were considered significant.

Results

Anti-inflammatory activity

In EA, the inhibition caused by PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC with a 10 µL concentration was (52% ± 0.943), 20 µL 61% ± 0.943, 30µL 68% ± 0.943, 40µL 68% ± 0.943, 50µL 76% ± 0.943 and for the standard, it was 55 ± 0.943, 64, 69%, 72%, 81% respectively for the above mentioned concentrations. The difference was statistically significant

Table 5: Comparison between antioxidant activity obtained in DPPH, H₂O₂ and FRAP

	Group	N	Mean	S.D.	S.E Mean	p value
DPPH 10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	63.45	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	66.25	0.007	0.002	
DPPH 20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	74.89	0.015	0.005	<0.001*
	Standard	10	78.52	0.007	0.002	
DPPH 30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	84.85	0.016	0.005	<0.001*
	Standard	10	85.63	0.008	0.003	
DPPH 40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	87.77	0.007	0.002	<0.001*
	Standard	10	88.68	0.007	0.002	
DPPH 50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	92.67	0.012	0.004	<0.001*
	Standard	10	93.15	0.007	0.002	
H ₂ O ₂ 10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	50.43	0.007	0.002	<0.001*
	Standard	10	51.10	0.082	0.026	
H ₂ O ₂ 20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	54.34	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	56.90	0.067	0.021	
H ₂ O ₂ 30µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	64.28	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	66.10	0.082	0.026	
H ₂ O ₂ 40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	75.77	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	78.80	0.082	0.026	
H ₂ O ₂ 50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	87.82	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	89.90	0.082	0.026	
FRAP 10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	50.43	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	51.10	0.082	0.026	
FRAP 20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	56.34	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	56.90	0.082	0.026	
FRAP 30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	65.28	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	66.10	0.082	0.026	
FRAP 40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	77.77	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	78.80	0.082	0.026	
FRAP 50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	10	88.82	0.008	0.003	<0.001*
	Standard	10	89.90	0.082	0.026	

p value <0.005 show statistical significance

($p < 0.001$). For BSA, the percentage of inhibition for the test material namely PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC was 43% for 10 µL, 57% for 20 µL, 69% for 30 µL, 75% for 40 µL and 80% for 50 µL for the control material the percentage of inhibition was 47%, 60%, 72%, 78%, 84% respectively ($p < 0.001$) (table 1). There were significant differences between the groups of different concentrations of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC in both EA and BSA except for 30 µL in EA ($p < 0.001$) (tables 2,3). On pair-wise Multiple comparison, a significant difference was found in EA and BSA between all the concentrations except in 30 and 40 µL in EA (table 4).

Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant activity observed for DPPH ranged from 63.455% to 92.67% in the test group and 66.25% to 93.15% with the standard. For H₂O₂ the values were 54.34% to 89.90% for the experimental group and 56.90% to 89.90% for the standard. For FRAP the values were 50.43% to 88.82% and 51.10% to 89.90% respectively (table 5). Significant difference was found between all the concentrations of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC. ($P < 0.001$) (tables

6,7). There were significant differences between the groups of different concentrations of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC in both DPPH, H₂O₂ and FRAP ($P < 0.001$) (table 8). On pairwise comparison, significant difference was found in all concentrations in all the three tests.

Discussion

Nanotechnology principles enabled the development of biomaterials that closely mimic the structure and composition of bone. These nanomaterials can serve as scaffolds that are similar to the extracellular matrix of bone and this facilitate direct interaction between cells and the scaffold and enhance tissue regeneration. Research findings have demonstrated that nanomaterials used for bone regeneration possess unique chemical and physical properties, which significantly improve osteoblast adhesion and proliferation [22]. Hence in the present study calcium sulphate nanomaterials and titanium dioxide nanoparticles were used to synthesise Pomegranate peel extract mediated calcium sulphate titanium dioxide nanocomposite (PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC).

Table 6: t-test for Equality of Means (DPPH, H₂O₂, FRAP)

% of inhibition		t-test for Equality of Means					95% Confidence Interval	
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Err Difference	Lower	Upper
DPPH 10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-840.000	18	<0.001*	-2.800	0.003	-2.807	-2.793
	Standard	-840.000	17.308		-2.800	0.003	-2.807	-2.793
DPPH 20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-702.946	18	<0.001*	-3.630	0.005	-3.641	-3.619
	Standard	-702.946	12.462		-3.630	0.005	-3.641	-3.619
DPPH 30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-139.842	18	<0.001*	-0.780	0.006	-0.792	-0.768
	Standard	-139.842	13.569		-0.780	0.006	-0.792	-0.768
DPPH 40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-305.223	18	<0.001*	-0.910	0.003	-0.916	-0.904
	Standard	-305.223	18.000		-0.910	0.003	-0.916	-0.904
DPPH 50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-107.331	18	<0.001*	-0.480	0.004	-0.489	-0.471
	Standard	-107.331	13.755		-0.480	0.004	-0.490	-0.470
H ₂ O ₂ 10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-25.863	18	<0.001*	-0.670	0.026	-0.724	-0.616
	Standard	-25.863	9.120		-0.670	0.026	-0.728	-0.612
H ₂ O ₂ 20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-120.531	18	<0.001*	-2.560	0.021	-2.605	-2.515
	Standard	-120.531	9.270		-2.560	0.021	-2.608	-2.512
H ₂ O ₂ 30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-70.138	18	<0.001*	-1.820	0.026	-1.875	-1.765
	Standard	-70.138	9.180		-1.820	0.026	-1.879	-1.761
H ₂ O ₂ 40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-116.769	18	<0.001*	-3.030	0.026	-3.085	-2.975
	Standard	-116.769	9.180		-3.030	0.026	-3.089	-2.971
H ₂ O ₂ 50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-80.158	18	<0.001*	-2.080	0.026	-2.135	-2.025
	Standard	-80.158	9.180		-2.080	0.026	-2.139	-2.021
FRAP 10 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-25.820	18	<0.001*	-0.670	0.026	-0.725	-0.615
	Standard	-25.820	9.180		-0.670	0.026	-0.729	-0.611
FRAP 20 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-21.581	18	<0.001*	-0.560	0.026	-0.615	-0.505
	Standard	-21.581	9.180		-0.560	0.026	-0.619	-0.501
FRAP 30 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-31.601	18	<0.001*	-0.820	0.026	-0.875	-0.765
	Standard	-31.601	9.180		-0.820	0.026	-0.879	-0.761
FRAP 40 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-39.694	18	<0.001*	-1.030	0.026	-1.085	-0.975
	Standard	-39.694	9.180		-1.030	0.026	-1.089	-0.971
FRAP 50 µL	PPE CaSO ₄ TiO ₂	-41.621	18	<0.001*	-1.080	0.026	-1.135	-1.025
	Standard	-41.621	9.180		-1.080	0.026	-1.139	-1.021

Table 7: Comparison between different concentrations of DPPH, H₂O₂, FRAP (ANOVA)

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
DPPH	Between Groups	5418.035	4	1354.509	9235287.273	<0.001*
	Within Groups	0.007	45	0.000		
	Total	5418.042	49			
H ₂ O ₂	Between Groups	9515.103	4	2378.776	38230323.750	<0.001*
	Within Groups	0.003	45	0.000		
	Total	9515.106	49			
FRAP	Between Groups	9806.143	4	2451.536	36773035.500	<0.001*
	Within Groups	0.003	45	0.000		
	Total	9806.146	49			

** p value <0.05 shows statistical significance

Table 8: Multiple comparisons made by Tukey HSD on values obtained in DPPH, H₂O₂, FRAP

	Concentration	Mean Difference	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval		
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
DPPH	10 µL	20 µL	-11.44000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-11.4554	-11.4246
		30 µL	-21.40000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-21.4154	-21.3846
		40 µL	-24.32000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-24.3354	-24.3046
		50 µL	-29.22000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-29.2354	-29.2046
	20 µL	10 µL	11.44000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	11.4246	11.4554
		30 µL	-9.96000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-9.9754	-9.9446
		40 µL	-12.88000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-12.8954	-12.8646
		50 µL	-17.78000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-17.7954	-17.7646
	30 µL	10 µL	21.40000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	21.3846	21.4154
		20 µL	9.96000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	9.9446	9.9754
		40 µL	-2.92000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-2.9354	-2.9046
		50 µL	-7.82000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-7.8354	-7.8046
	40 µL	10 µL	24.32000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	24.3046	24.3354
		20 µL	12.88000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	12.8646	12.8954
		30 µL	2.92000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	2.9046	2.9354
		50 µL	-4.90000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	-4.9154	-4.8846
	50 µL	10 µL	29.22000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	29.2046	29.2354
		20 µL	17.78000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	17.7646	17.7954
		30 µL	7.82000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	7.8046	7.8354
		40 µL	4.90000 [*]	0.00542	<0.001*	4.8846	4.9154
H ₂ O ₂	10 µL	20 µL	-3.91000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-3.9200	-3.9000
		30 µL	-13.85000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-13.8600	-13.8400
		40 µL	-25.34000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-25.3500	-25.3300
		50 µL	-37.39000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-37.4000	-37.3800
	20 µL	10 µL	3.91000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	3.9000	3.9200
		30 µL	-9.94000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-9.9500	-9.9300
		40 µL	-21.43000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-21.4400	-21.4200
		50 µL	-33.48000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-33.4900	-33.4700
	30 µL	10 µL	13.85000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	13.8400	13.8600
		20 µL	9.94000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	9.9300	9.9500
		40 µL	-11.49000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-11.5000	-11.4800
		50 µL	-23.54000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-23.5500	-23.5300
	40 µL	10 µL	25.34000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	25.3300	25.3500
		20 µL	21.43000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	21.4200	21.4400
		30 µL	11.49000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	11.4800	11.5000
		50 µL	-12.05000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	-12.0600	-12.0400
	50 µL	10 µL	37.39000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	37.3800	37.4000
		20 µL	33.48000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	33.4700	33.4900
		30 µL	23.54000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	23.5300	23.5500
		40 µL	12.05000 [*]	0.00353	<0.001*	12.0400	12.0600

Calcium sulphate has been utilized as a bone regenerative material because of its proven biocompatibility, biodegradability, osteoconductivity, and angiogenic potential. However, some authors have pointed out that it has rapid resorption rate, and limited regenerative capacity which could restrict its application as an effective regenerative material. The particle size of the material has a

significant impact on its properties; therefore, adopting its nano form could address the limitations. By utilizing the principles of nanotechnology, calcium sulphate nanoparticles exhibited enhanced physical properties [23]. Calcium sulphate nanoparticles could serve as scaffolds for bone regeneration, offering a large surface area for growth factor adsorption and a controlled release of adsorbed materials. Nano particles also provide superior strength, promote

Table 8 (cont.): Multiple comparisons made by Tukey HSD on values obtained in DPPH, H₂O₂, FRAP

	20 µL	-5.91000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-5.9204	-5.8996
	30 µL	-14.85000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-14.8604	-14.8396
	40 µL	-27.34000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-27.3504	-27.3296
	50 µL	-38.39000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-38.4004	-38.3796
10 µL	10 µL	5.91000*	0.00365	<0.001*	5.8996	5.9204
	30 µL	-8.94000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-8.9504	-8.9296
	40 µL	-21.43000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-21.4404	-21.4196
	50 µL	-32.48000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-32.4904	-32.4696
20 µL	10 µL	14.85000*	0.00365	<0.001*	14.8396	14.8604
	20 µL	8.94000*	0.00365	<0.001*	8.9296	8.9504
	40 µL	-12.49000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-12.5004	-12.4796
	50 µL	-23.54000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-23.5504	-23.5296
30 µL	10 µL	27.34000*	0.00365	<0.001*	27.3296	27.3504
	20 µL	21.43000*	0.00365	<0.001*	21.4196	21.4404
	30 µL	12.49000*	0.00365	<0.001*	12.4796	12.5004
	50 µL	-11.05000*	0.00365	<0.001*	-11.0604	-11.0396
40 µL	10 µL	38.39000*	0.00365	<0.001*	38.3796	38.4004
	20 µL	32.48000*	0.00365	<0.001*	32.4696	32.4904
	30 µL	23.54000*	0.00365	<0.001*	23.5296	23.5504
	40 µL	11.05000*	0.00365	<0.001*	11.0396	11.0604

** p value <0.05 shows statistical significance

optimal osteoconductivity and resistance to fractures [24]. The nanoparticles have proven their effectiveness as graft materials in bilateral sinus lift augmentation procedures, either as a standalone material or in combination with platelet-rich fibrin. It has also been reported that the injectable paste form of calcium sulphate nanoparticles stimulate bone formation and serve as an efficient vehicle for stem cells. When combined with bone morphogenetic proteins and mesenchymal stem cells, calcium sulphate nanoparticles enhance osteogenesis in critical bone defects and demonstrate significant potential for different clinical applications [25].

Investigators have proved that both pure and pigment forms of titanium dioxide are equally biocompatible, have good osteoconductive properties and can be effectively used in the augmentation of osseous defects. TiO₂ nanostructures, like titania nanotubes (NTs), are used for surface coating of implants. TiO₂ NTs have good stability against disintegration and reduce swelling and can be used as a smart delivery system for controlled drug release in implants [26]. The porous structure of TiO₂ NTs enhances bone regeneration and repair, and this favours the bone growth and osseointegration of implants. TiO₂ nanotube surface favours osteoblast adhesion and exhibits an ability to bind to bone [27].

Pomegranate peel is abundant with biologically active compounds namely - flavonoids like anthocyanins, flavons and flavonols, - tannins like ellagitannins such as ellagic acid, gallic acid, punicalagin and punicalin and - organic acids and alkaloids. Presence of these biologically active compounds cause high antioxidant and hydroxyl radical scavenging activity [28]. Pomegranate peel extract substantially stimulates osteoblastic MC3T3-E1 alkaline phosphatase activity and can prevent decrease in bone mineral density [29]. The administration of pomegranate extract to ovariectomised mice normalised bone mineral density and increased bone volume and trabecular number. Flavonoids and isoflavone compounds

accelerated bone healing and showed acceptable bone growth in the defect region,

Both calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide are osteoconductive materials. Pomegranate peel extract enhances osteoblastic activity and accelerates bone healing. Therefore, in the present study pomegranate peel extract based calcium sulphate titanium dioxide nano composite was synthesized and its biological properties namely anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties were evaluated.

In the present study, egg albumin denaturation assay and bovine serum albumin denaturation assay were used to measure the anti-inflammatory properties of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC. Protein denaturation causes inflammation. Evaluation of the effect of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC in controlling the anti-inflammatory activity showed that the extract inhibited protein denaturation. In all the assays of EA and BSA, there was statistically significant difference between the test material and the standard ie. diclofenac sodium (p<0.05). Even though the test and the control materials showed statistically significant difference in all the concentrations, the mean values obtained for the test and standard were more or less similar. It was also found that the test as well as the standard material showed an increase in the anti-inflammatory properties, when the concentration of the materials increased. It could be observed that at higher concentrations, the difference between the test and the standard was restricted to below 1%. Therefore it can be concluded that the anti-inflammatory activity was concentration dependent. The results obtained with PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC were comparable to the commercial drug which was used. In other words, PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC has anti-inflammatory properties similar to that of the standard ie. diclofenac sodium.

The antioxidant activity was measured using DPPH, H₂O₂ assay and FRAP assay, the standard used was ascorbic acid. In all the

tested concentrations used, significant difference was found between PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC and the standard (P<0.05) but when the numerical mean values were compared, they were almost similar. It was also seen that at higher concentrations of 30, 40 and 50 μ L, the difference in mean numerical values were less than 2%; between the test material and the standard in DPPH, H₂O₂ and FRAP. This indicates equivalence between the standard and the test groups in the above mentioned concentrations. (p<0.05).

It was also found that the antioxidant activity increased, as the concentration increased from 10 μ L to 50 μ L. Significant difference was found in all the concentrations with all the three tests (P<0.05). This shows that the antioxidant properties increased with the increase in concentration ie the antioxidant activity is dose dependent and the PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC could provide antioxidant activity similar to the standard. This finding is similar to the findings of previous studies which concluded that pomegranate peel extract has high concentration of biologically active compounds responsible for the antioxidant activity. Concentration of the compounds depends on the method of extraction and the cultivar and the antioxidant activity increases with the concentration of the peel extract [30]. It can also be stated that addition of calcium sulphate and titanium dioxide nanoparticles did not decrease the antioxidative property as the values obtained were comparable with the standard used.

Conclusion

Pomegranate's unique biochemical composition, rich in bioactive components, provides notable anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. The antioxidant activity of PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC was found to be comparable to that of the control and demonstrated a concentration-dependent relationship. Additionally, the extract's ability to inhibit protein denaturation highlights its anti-inflammatory potential, which also varies with concentration. This study suggests that PPE CaSO₄ TiO₂ NC exhibits significant anti-inflammatory and antioxidant characteristics influenced by its concentration. These findings contribute to the understanding of pomegranate's therapeutic potential. However, comprehensive testing is necessary before its bioactive compounds can be utilized, either individually or in combination, as therapeutic agents for treating various degenerative conditions, such as osteoporosis and rheumatoid arthritis, or for promoting bone regeneration.

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